

RESEARCH REPORT
2025
TREPA Series 31-2025

Social Science Fieldwork
Order of Operations: South Africa 2024

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TREPA

**Threat Reduction for the
Environment, People, and Animals**

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CITE THIS DOCUMENT:

Fenio, K, Hübschle, A, Dabezies, JM. 2025. *Social Science Fieldwork Order of Operations: 2024*. Threat Reduction for the Environment, People and Animals. Department of Geographical Sciences, College of Behavioral and Social Sciences, University of Maryland, College Park. College Park, MD. 13 pp.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

TREPA is grateful for Kruger National Park's support for the successful development of its research activities. It specifically acknowledges the professionalism and support provided by Aubrey Maluleke, Edson Mutele, and Fanie Phandavhudzi, without whom this research wouldn't have been possible. TREPA would also like to express its appreciation to the local community leaders in the Mutele, Makuya, and Mukuleke areas who facilitated TREPA's research activities and to the data enumerators whose work and dedication were paramount for the success of this research.

The research, methods, and analysis detailed in this document were reviewed and granted approval by (i) the University of Cape Town's Law Research Ethics Committee, (ii) the Institutional Review Boards of the University of Maryland, College Park, University of Texas Austin, University of Alabama and Colorado State University, (iii) Witwatersrand University's Human Research Ethics Committee (non-medical) H24/03/10, (iv) the Office of Human Research Oversight OHRO Log Number E05089 and permissions from the Traditional Councils of the Makuleke, Mutele, and Makuya communities.

This material is based upon work supported by the United States Department of Defense, Defense Threat Reduction Agency. Any opinions, findings, and conclusions or recommendations expressed in this publication are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the views of the federal government, and no official endorsement should be inferred.

INTRODUCTION

This document reflects the details pursuant to which social science data collection activities were conducted in Mutele, Makuya, and Makuleke communities around Kruger National Park (KNP), South Africa, in November 2024.

The team of researchers present during these activities were Dr. Annette Hübschle, Dr. Juan Martín Dabezies, Dr. Matt Kammer-Kerwick, and Dr. Kenly Greer Fenio. Research activities took place November 11-19, 2024. A Mission Report on this fieldwork season is available on TREPA's website: www.conservationcriminology.com/TREPA under Scholarly Products.

The research team spent three days in each of the three local communities, which were designated as the "TREPA Days," with different activities conducted on each day. This document provides the details on the timeline and how these activities were conducted. As the structure was the same in each community, the main part of the document is structured according to these TREPA Days.

ORDER OF OPERATIONS

Setting up TREPA days

Prior to the fieldwork, Dr. Annette Hübschle met with the traditional leaders of the Makuleke and Mutele communities to re-acquaint them with the TREPA project as more than a year had passed since research permissions had been obtained from the then-traditional leadership in the participating communities. The Makuya community was embroiled in leadership changes at the time of fieldwork, so Mr. Fanie Phandavhudzi facilitated communications with the acting leadership. Through Mr. Aubrey Makuleke, Mr. Edson Mutele, and Mr. Fanie Phandavhudzi, the community engagement practitioners assisting the TREPA team, and helped identify community-owned and run catering businesses to provide meals to the TREPA team and research participants during the TREPA days. Mr Makuleke, Mr Mutele, and Mr Phandavhudzi also assisted with the recruitment of four data enumerators in each community ahead of the fieldwork (18-19 October 2024).

TREPA Day 1

1. Meeting with Data Enumerators

The first activity in each area was to meet the four data enumerators who would work with TREPA in each community (a total of 12 for three communities). The data enumerators were residents of each community; this provided the TREPA team with the opportunity to train, teach, and hire local residents. They underwent training each day before the beginning of each activity and were compensated with \$40 (R800) per day.

2. Introductory Meeting with Local Leader(s) and Data Enumerators

The data collection activities started in each community center with a meeting with the local leader(s) and/or community engagement practitioner for Kruger National Park (KNP). Dr. Hübschle began the proceedings by introducing the TREPA team to the data enumerators, providing a brief explanation of how the activities would unfold and important timelines.

The team stressed that each research activity sought to generate information on the interaction between people, domestic animals, wildlife, and the environment, with the following key messages:

- Project Topics: TREPA is framed within the One Health paradigm, focusing on disease transmission, anthrax, the role of wildlife, and the interaction between wildlife and humans concerning disease transmission (including poaching and regarding the legal or illegal aspects of human practices).
- Research Project: TREPA is a research project aimed at answering scientific questions. The knowledge generated would be crucial for decision-making and improving residents' quality of life.
- Timeline and Research Outcomes: TREPA is a long-term project so immediate results should not be expected; patience is required as the team analyzes data to determine findings.

- **Community Activity Schedule:** The team highlighted the types of activities and the days on which they would take place.
- **Research ethics:** Data enumerators and research participants were introduced to research ethics—including informed consent, anonymity, confidentiality, data management and other ethical cornerstones—that govern the TREPA project.
- **Informed consent:** Participation in the activities would be entirely voluntary and TREPA would not offer direct compensation for participation. Participants could withdraw at any time and could choose which questions to answer.
- **Integration with Meals:** TREPA would provide lunch as a shared meal (and in Makuya, breakfast as well) hoping they would be appreciated by the communities.
- **Acknowledgment to Data Enumerators:** This included the introduction, indicating that the local researchers come from the communities, and acknowledging appreciation for their assistance.
- **Acknowledgment to Community Leaders and General Community:** This focused on thanking the community leaders and the community at large for participating in the activities.
- **Respecting Schedules:** This highlighted the importance of adhering to schedules to ensure that activities run smoothly.
- **Spatial Needs:** Highlighting that some activities required chairs; tables; and a quiet, enclosed space for discussions that could be recorded (e.g. the Focus Group Discussions [FGDs]).
- **Debrief:** Each research activity would be followed by a short feedback session with participants and enumerators.

The local leader(s) and researchers then had the opportunity to ask any questions, provide recommendations, or share any comments on the project or the activities.

3. General Data Enumerator Training

Dr. Hübschle provided general training for data enumerators based on the training documents. Broadly, she explained the importance of:

- **Politeness and welcoming manners with participants:** She explained that data enumerators were mandated to respect different opinions, worldviews, and cultural differences if any (e.g., perceptions of activities and livelihoods).
- **Informed consent and the right of every participant to determine if they wanted to participate,** the right to withdraw at any time, the right to refuse to answer a question, the anonymous base of most of the data collection instruments (except for the Social Networks Survey, where providing a contact would be optional) and that information would be deleted after the project ends.
- **The concept of confidential information:** the importance of data enumerators not talking with any third party about the development of the data collection, participant answers, or any confidential information provided by TREPA. Data enumerators would be required to sign a document reflecting their obligations to maintain confidential

information. This was an informal Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA)¹ and the extent of the obligations they would be bound to comply with if they chose to execute the agreement. She indicated where to sign if they agreed with the agreement's content.

- After the NDA was signed, they would each be paid \$40 (R800) a day as follows:
 - \$40 (R800) for the first day, paid in advance on the morning of the first day;
 - \$80 (R1600) for the second and third day of work, payable by the end of Day 3 when all work is completed.
- On Day 3 the enumerators would receive a certificate indicating they had completed training and certifying the hours worked for TREPA as research data enumerators. This was done with the hope that the training would allow them to certify their experience for future projects seeking research support in their communities and beyond.

4. Structured Interviews Training: Using KoBo Toolbox

Following the general data enumerator training, the TREPA team trained the enumerators on conducting the structured interviews on an Android Tablet with the KoBo Collect software platform. This training occurred as follows:

- The training researcher (Dr. Hübschle) handed out a tablet to each enumerator while keeping one tablet to use as guidance.
- The training researcher indicated the password (1234) to access the tablet, which would be easy to remember. For ease of reference, the tablets also had the passwords written on the back.
- Enumerators and the training researcher verified that the tablets were sufficiently charged.
- The training researcher indicated the KoBo app located on the tablet's screen and how to start a new survey by clicking the blue button titled "start new form."
- The training researcher instructed the enumerators to click on the TREPA survey to start and then click the button "go to start".
- The training researcher then read the survey guidance in English and explained that the first two questions of the survey were icebreakers and that these should be asked to participants to better help them understand the survey.
- The training researcher then asked the enumerators the survey questions in English as if she were conducting the survey, as enumerators followed the interview and marked the answers on their own tablets.
- The training researcher noted words or questions which were difficult to follow or understand and requested any insights on the questions themselves (e.g., insight such as "people will not answer anything about hunting in a buffer zone where it is forbidden").
- The training researcher had the enumerators ask each other the interview questions in Venda or Tsonga. The enumerators translated from English on the tablets to these local

¹ This procedure was based on previous experience by team members with data enumerators on similar topics in similar geographies in the region. The tone of the procedure was to add an additional layer of protection for the research participants, team members, and data enumerators. The document was not binding nor a legal document.

languages (Venda was used in Mutele and Makuya, while Tsonga was used in Makuleke). During this part of the training, she told enumerators about the importance of providing the answer options to participants. She also answered questions on the scope of the interview, clarified concepts or particular words, assessed the accuracy of how the enumerators marked the answers on the tablet, and reassured the data enumerators that this was a learning process and that it was okay to make mistakes.

- The training researcher explained that the demographic questions section was not mandatory, and that the survey would still be valid if participants declined to answer those questions.
- To reflect that the surveys completed during the training should not be considered for data collection and analysis purposes, all enumerators were instructed to mark the age of the training participant as “100.” This would allow researchers to discard these questionnaires from the collected data during the analysis phase.
- The enumerators were told the interviews would initially take about 45 minutes each while they familiarized themselves with the tool and became more comfortable with the data collection process. After this, the average time to answer the questionnaires would be 20-30 minutes.

5. Structured Interviews Data Collection

The structured interviews in South Africa were conducted smoothly, with an appropriate recruitment process and engagement from local participants. The enumerators, who were carefully selected for their language proficiency and prior research experience, played a crucial role in facilitating the process. They were well-trained in using KoBo Toolbox, ensuring data collection was efficient and ethically conducted.

Participants were recruited through community outreach efforts, with a focus on maintaining gender balance and age diversity. The approach of conducting interviews in open spaces, where community members felt comfortable, contributed to a high response rate and meaningful engagement. While some minor challenges arose—such as instances where enumerators initially conducted group interviews rather than individual ones, and variations in data collection speeds—these were quickly identified and addressed through additional training and oversight. The research team closely monitored data quality, flagging and reviewing any unusually short interviews to ensure validity.

Overall, the structured interviews provided valuable insights into community perceptions of human-wildlife interactions, disease risks, and conservation efforts. The experience reaffirmed the effectiveness of working closely with local enumerators to ensure culturally appropriate and reliable data collection. Moreover, the enthusiasm and engagement of the enumerators highlighted opportunities for future capacity-building and continued collaboration with local researchers.

6. Social Network Survey Training

Dr. Dabezies (Community 1), Dr. Matt Kammer-Kerwick (Communities 1 and 2) and/or Dr. Kenly Greer Fenio (Community 3) started this training by indicating that while it was a similar tool to the one on the tablets, this survey was paper-based. This tool was deployed in English and the researchers were instructed to think about how to ask the questions in the local language. They explained that this would be the only data collection tool where names would be recorded, unlike the other tools deployed, since this tool is expected to be repeated to the same individuals next year, but that this was still optional for the respondents. Participants would also be asked to complete the informed consent agreeing to participate, but that they could do so either in writing or verbally. The enumerators were instructed to write in “Provided Verbal Response” in the latter cases.

The trainers indicated that these surveys would take about 45 minutes to one hour with each respondent and that this should be communicated to participants. Instructions were also given regarding the 7-point Likert scales, that participants would be required to choose the frequency of certain activities, that the survey had yes/no response options to questions, and that there were questions with a general statement applicable to multiple answer options, as well as fill-in-the-blank questions. (Note: the latter were dropped during the first training because they made the questionnaire too long for the respondents to remain actively engaged.) Enumerators were trained on how to use a water bottle to indicate the differences in Likert response options so as to make the theoretical constructs easier for respondents to understand. The bottle was used to indicate the degree of completeness of something, for example: "if the bottle is full, then it means that it is the maximum, that is a 7. On the other hand, if the bottle is missing some water, but less than half then it can be a 2 or a 3.

The training researcher went through each of the questions with the enumerators following a similar methodology used during the tablet-based surveys, that is: 1) explaining each question in English; 2) discussing the questions or wording that posed difficult language; 3) concepts and the reasoning behind the questions; 4) the Social Network analysis tool at the end, which was discussed extensively regarding goals.

In the third community, Dr. Fenio added more training to fully discuss some of the questions that posed problems in the second community and which either the enumerators or respondents did not adequately understand. She also had the two Social Network enumerators practice with the other two KoBo enumerators so that there was a full test run with the questions on respondents who had not seen the questionnaire; these “respondents” were told to ask for clarification on any questions they did not fully understand. During this “pilot,” Dr. Fenio and Dr. Dabezies worked with the enumerators to address any additional challenges.

7. Social Network Survey Activity Deployment

The conduct of these interviews was very similar to the Structured Interview data collection. The activities were carried out with pen/paper. Since the Likert scale was 7 points (instead of 3 as was the case with the tablet questionnaire), interpreting the score to be assigned to the response was more complex, and the data enumerators needed greater support (e.g. the use

of the water bottle as a visual example). Additionally, support was needed for the various types of questions (in addition to Likert scales, there were yes/no questions, open-ended questions, and frequency selection questions), and the somewhat confusing wording of some of them for respondents.

TREPA Day 2

1. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) Training

On the morning of Day 2, the training for the FGDs emphasized the roles of each enumerator (two enumerators per group). One enumerator was trained to navigate the dynamics of responses and conversations while translating the FGD guide into the local language and probing for additional responses when necessary. The second enumerator was trained to translate the responses to the FGD guide questions for the researchers: for the FGD with questions on One Health, Dr. Hübschle listened to the translation while in the second FGD, Drs. Dabezies and Kammer-Kerwick listened to the translation by the enumerator.

2. FGD Activity Deployment

In the initial stage, all participants from both FGDs were gathered in one place, and the following topics were explained:

- The objectives of the TREPA project
- Participation as voluntary and anonymous
- Consent for a recording that would be used solely for scientific purposes to enable an in-depth transcript and subsequent analysis of the collected testimonies

In both FGDs, participants sat in a circle with the recorder placed in the middle. Each group was composed of 5-10 people, with a medium to high degree of gender parity and age diversity. Both FGDs were conducted in parallel in two different spaces. In the FGD with questions on Social Networks, Drs. Dabezies and Kammer-Kerwick and two data enumerators participated, while in the FGD with questions on One Health, Dr. Hübschle and two data enumerators were involved.

One enumerator translated the English FGD questionnaire into the local language while the second loosely translated responses for the senior team members. As necessary, the senior team member or local researcher clarified or probed for additional information during the discussions. The senior researchers largely sat in the background, apart from the participants' circle, along with the translator. The researchers took notes as appropriate, managed the timing, and assisted in navigating the discussions.

TREPA Day 3

1. Participatory Risk Mapping (PRM) Training

The third day in each community started with Dr. Dabezies training the enumerators on PRM. For this training and later development of the activity, the research team organized the room(s) by separating desks to form three groups. Then they trained the enumerators by

providing them with a general overview of the activity: e.g., during today's activity, the researcher will be asking participants different questions on health, livestock, and wildlife, and the researcher will ask that all answers be reflected on the map with a different symbol for each answer.

The specific study site maps were laid out on a table, and enumerators were asked to familiarize themselves with the maps. They were specifically asked to pinpoint where their community was located. Some enumerators were unfamiliar with maps, and on those occasions, the research team explained that maps are how land is seen from the sky, just like an image/photo taken from above. They explained that maps have scales and that the small-scale map covered more area than the large-scale map being used. Then, the researchers explained that maps usually have legends. Dr. Dabezies explained a legend by using the existing legend on the maps that identified villages, schools, airports, and some health facilities.

Dr. Dabezies explained that each answer to a question asked by the researchers should have a symbol, which would be put into the map legend: *"For example, we will be asking participants to mark on the maps where elephants live."* The researcher then mimicked with a pen how participants might answer. Symbols were to be chosen freely by the participants and could be any type of shape, letter, or number. Enumerators were told that all information provided by the participants needed to be recorded on the maps. They were instructed that participants did not need to agree on everything, and that each participant's opinion was valid. Participants could discuss the answers before marking them down, but consensus was not required. If divergent opinions arose, each participant could mark their answer and reflect it on the map. Enumerators were also told that participants could start off marking places with pencils, and then filling them in with the colored markers provided.

Enumerators were instructed to help orient participants (e.g. understand the map, villages, and existing landmarks) but that they should not provide answers, as their role was only to facilitate and support. For every answer, and thus symbol reflected on the maps, they needed to create a legend on the back of the physical maps and the legend should be sufficiently descriptive (e.g., *"D=where domestic animals drink"*). At the end of the training, each enumerator was assigned to one group, and the researcher asked the enumerators to suggest which of the two maps would be easiest and most convenient to start with.

2. PRM Activity Development

The PRM consisted of three groups of roughly 5-7 people each. The team had two maps per group with scales and imagery (e.g., street and topography maps). The activity began with one enumerator leading each group. Participants were informed about the goals of the research and that the activity would last approximately two to three hours. Dr. Dabezies spoke in English with one of the four local enumerators translating into the local language. The introduction to the activity covered the following:

- A brief introduction that this activity was being held as part of a research project called TREPA and that the activity was called participatory mapping. Research was defined as collecting information and learning more about their communities and ways of living.
- Participants were told that TREPA is a project that is researching the One Health topic; this is a concept whereby there is only one health between people, domestic animals, wildlife, and the environment. The researcher explained that on their tables, they had an image of what this concept looked like. The researcher then went to each table explaining the One Health image and how the Venn diagram between human, animal, and environmental health forms One Health.
- Information regarding informed consent and that participants could leave at any time without explanation.
- All participants could participate equitably and were told that all opinions were valid and there were no right or wrong answers.
- An overview of participatory mapping, involving Dr. Dabezies asking some questions, which participants would answer by drawing symbols—any figures, letters, or numbers—on the maps. In all three locations, the researcher told the participants that they were free to choose any symbols to use.
- The researcher then held a map in front of everyone and mimicked how to answer the questions on it. He explained that the data enumerators would support the participants by creating a legend on the back of the maps. The researcher then folded the map and mimicked writing the legend, indicating that the importance of a legend was for the research team to understand the meaning allocated by the participants to each symbol.
- Once instructions were provided, Dr. Dabezies asked all participants to identify their community/village on the maps. While they were identifying their communities/villages, he walked around the room observing the groups. After they identified their community, he wrote the community names on all maps to show the participants that it was okay to write on the maps and break the ice for the remainder of the activity.
- Dr. Dabezies then followed the protocol questions. While participants discussed and answered questions, he observed the groups, looking at the answers provided and ensuring that legends were completed.
- Once the groups finished answering the questions, the research team collected the maps, thanked the participants for their contributions, and opened a space for them to share their feedback on how the experience had been for them. They also requested recommendations on how to conduct this activity with other communities. Participants shared their views on the activity and/or asked questions about the project and the benefits it would bring to the communities.
- Once the activity was completed, the maps with plastic covers and the legend sheets were digitized.

3. Closing Meeting

After sharing lunch with the community and enumerators on Day 3, a closing meeting was held with the TREPA research team and enumerators to conclude the TREPA Days. It consisted

of a debriefing session with any additional feedback, thanking the enumerators, finalizing payments, and the distribution of training certificates.

Refusals and Withdrawals

There were no refusals to participate in the FGDs or the mapping exercises. There were some refusals in the social network surveys to give names/contact details.

Conclusion and Future Considerations

The 2024 TREPA fieldwork in South Africa successfully gathered critical insights on the intersection of human-wildlife interactions, biosafety, and conservation practices using a participatory, community-centered approach. The research benefited significantly from strong local partnerships, including the support of traditional leaders, data enumerators, and outreach coordinators.

Despite some logistical and methodological challenges, the adaptability of the research team ensured high-quality data collection. The structured interviews, social network surveys, and participatory mapping activities provided valuable findings, while the FGDs allowed for in-depth exploration of local perceptions regarding health, conservation, and disease transmission risks.

Key takeaways from this fieldwork include:

- **Effective local capacity-building:** Data enumerators not only contributed to data collection but also developed valuable research skills, with many expressing interest in further training.
- **Adaptability in research design:** Minor modifications in participant recruitment, research tools, and training helped to improve the quality and depth of responses.
- **Strengthening research ethics practices:** Maintaining informed consent and transparency in research goals helped build community trust.

Moving forward, TREPA aims to continue refining research methodologies, enhancing participant recruitment strategies, and fostering ongoing engagement with local communities. Future research phases will integrate these lessons to further improve ethical and impactful fieldwork practices.